

H.263 VIDEO ENCODER IMPLEMENTATION ON A SCALABLE DSP SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

A mapping and realization of H.263 video encoder for video conferencing applications are given using our DSP based multiprocessor system, called PARNEU. PARNEU system is built for computationally intensive applications like image and video processing as well as soft computing applications. PARNEU has flexible communication architecture and thus it allows different mapping possibilities. The presented data parallel mapping has low communication and memory requirements, which allows encoding of any of the five standard H.263 picture formats. With a prototype system using four ADSP-21062 DSPs, a real-time encoding is achieved with QCIF sized picture. Phase times for each step of H.263 encoder are presented.

1. INTRODUCTION

H.263 standard [1] is meant for low bit rate video compression, which is an important part of video conferencing [2]. H.263 and its variations can be used in portable devices. The increased compression ratio, however, usually means higher computational requirements. Currently, communication bandwidth seems to be the most restrictive limitation, and thus increased computational requirements are accepted. Application specific integrated circuits (ASICs) would reach the performance, but the flexibility for algorithm modification is lost. Therefore, programmable solutions using one or multiple Digital Signal Processors (DSP) have gained significant interests. DSP based platform offers fast development time and a cost-effective solution, even though a real-time encoding is difficult to achieve [3]. A parallel DSP implementation will reach the real-time performance and illustrate the power that can be seen in the future implementations.

This paper describes parallel mapping possibilities of the H.263 video encoder and gives a detailed analysis of our results with the multiple DSP PARNEU system. Section 2 gives an overview of PARNEU. Section 3 describes parallel mappings of the H.263 algorithm. Communication requirements in multiprocessor environment are given in Section 4 and computational needs are analyzed in Section 5. PARNEU implementation and its performance results are presented in Section 6. Section 7 concludes the paper.

2. PARNEU SYSTEM

PARNEU [4] is a linearly scalable parallel computer system. It consists of modular processing cards each carrying four DSPs connected to a master controller and further to a host computer, as depicted in Figure 1. The host computer, which is used for initialisation and monitoring, is a PC with WindowsNT operating system. The host computer has also an Internet server to allow remote execution. The master PU controls the operations inside the PARNEU system.

The PARNEU hardware is implemented with Analog Device's ADSP-21062 digital signal processors [10] working as processing

units (PUs) and Xilinx field programmable gate arrays (FPGA) that perform the communication operations. Each PU has an internal 256 kilobytes SRAM memory that is used for program and data storage. This distributed memory system is programmed using communication primitives packed in C-language libraries. Same program multiple data (SPMD) programming concept with message passing is used. The communication network is hidden behind communication primitives.

In the design of PARNEU hardware, efficient communication has played a major role. A *global bus* connects all cards to the master for efficient broadcast operation. A *serial ring bus* connects each DSP to adjacent ones. Thus, data can be circulated between PUs in a systolic way. The third way to move data is a reconfigurable *partial tree structure* that is formed from the FPGAs. The tree network can perform global reduction operations as well as pre- or post-processing operations if external devices, like cameras, are connected. The FPGAs can be configured at run-time via the serial port of the PUs.

Figure 1. Block diagram of the PARNEU computer system.

3. PARALLEL MAPPINGS OF H.263

Control parallelism and data parallelism are the two basic parallelization concepts. In the control parallel method, the algorithm is divided into many parallel threads that are computed simultaneously. This method is commonly used in automatic parallelizers [5]. Data-parallel method has only a single control flow, but the same operations are done simultaneously to many data blocks. Data-parallel concepts can be well used in SPMD systems with message-passing communication like in PARNEU. In general, an image consists of almost independent image pixels that are suitable for data parallel implementation. However, in H.263 encoding dependencies come from the image streams.

Sequential images of the data stream are needed for motion estimation, which requires information from the previously reconstructed image. In addition, the bitstream must be constructed sequentially due to data dependencies, which are caused by storing the motion vectors differentially. Therefore, communication requirements due to data dependencies have to be considered carefully. Next we will present different projection possibilities and analyze their communication requirements.

Horizontal (row-wise) and vertical (column-wise) projections using the macroblock (MB) boundaries are the simplest mapping methods. The neighboring processors handle adjacent slice regions and data dependencies are limited to the neighboring PUs. Each PU needs only to swap overlapping motion estimation areas with two adjacent processors. This simple partitioning leads to an even distribution of MBs, when the number of columns or rows of MBs is high and the number of PUs is low. Because the number of columns is higher than the number of rows, the column-wise mapping is preferred. However, a column is quite large computational unit and the columns cannot always be divided equally to each PU, which leads to load imbalance.

The load balance can be improved when the row and column boundaries are not strictly followed. The whole row or column can be split to two processors as long as data dependencies are restricted to adjacent PUs and thus allow local communication. As an example, Figure 2 illustrates an improved column-wise mapping of QCIF picture to four PUs. The gray areas show the overlapped MBs that need to be changed between neighboring PUs 1 and 2. The MB division is started at the upper left corner of the picture and proceeds downwards until enough blocks are sent. The first MBs are sent to the first PU, the next MBs are sent to the second PU and so on. In the optimal case all PUs have the same number of MBs.

1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4
1	1	1	2	2	2	3	3	3	4	4

Figure 2. An example of macroblock distribution between PUs. Gray MBs indicate reconstructed MBs, which need to be interchanged between adjacent PUs 1 and 2. The numbers inside a matrix indicate the PU, which encodes the MB.

4. COMMUNICATION REQUIREMENTS

Efficient communication plays an essential role in parallel systems. Especially when the system is designed to be linearly expandable, specific attention must be paid to minimizing communication requirements and to utilizing local communication.

Communication requirements can be divided into local and global communication. The goal is to reduce global communication to allow algorithm scalability as the number of processors is increased. Special hardware components can be used to improve some global communication operations like global reduction and broadcast operations.

In data parallel implementation, MBs are mostly computed independently, but data transfer is needed to distribute the original data stream to each processor as well as to collect the partially

constructed bitstreams from the processing units. In the computation phase, neighboring processors need to change the MBs that belong to other processor's motion estimation area. First each PU encodes and reconstructs its own MBs. However, in the motion estimation stage of the next frame, other processors need these reconstructed MBs. To do motion estimation for one MB in the standard motion vector range, 9 MBs from the previous reconstructed frame are required. These nine MBs are situated at the same spatial location as the current MB and the macroblocks surrounding it in the previous frame.

Bitstream construction is the final step in the encoding process of one MB. It is computationally fairly light operation, but it has to be done in a linear manner. Processors can perform variable length coding to the quantized discrete cosine transform (DCT) coefficients independently and after that the master processor combines the partial results. The master encodes the motion vector differences and unifies the sub-bitstreams.

In Table 1, the communication requirements for different picture sizes are computed for bus based system, which does not benefit from local communication. The system consists of broadcast operation, and thus the same data block can be sent to all processors simultaneously. The communication requirements consist of distributing the current picture and the previous picture to all processors as well as sending the reconstructed data to the controller. The amount of encoded bitstream data varies depending on the motion estimation and the picture sequence, but in general the communication requirements to transfer bitstream are very small and thus it is excluded from Table 1. Altogether this means that to encode one picture the communication bandwidth required is about three times the size of the picture. This poses great demands on the communication network.

Table 1 Picture sizes and communication bandwidth requirements for one picture encoding and for real-time encoding with 30 frames per second (fps) with global bus architecture.

Picture size	Picture size in kilobytes	Bandwidth per one picture	Bandwidth to encode 30 fps
Sub-QCIF	18 KB	54 KB/s	1.6 MB/s
QCIF	37.125 KB	111.375 KB/s	3.3 MB/s
CIF	148.5 KB	445.5 KB/s	13.1 MB/s
4CIF	594 KB	1782 KB/s	52.2 MB/s
16CIF	2376 KB	7128 KB/s	208.8 MB/s

Table 2 Communication requirements to encode 30 frames per second using simultaneous global and local communication channels.

Picture size	Global bus bandwidth to encode 30 fps	Ring bus bandwidth per processor to encode 30 fps
Sub-QCIF	0.5 MB / s	315 KB / s
QCIF	1.1 MB / s	450 KB / s
CIF	4.4 MB / s	855 KB / s
4CIF	17.4 MB / s	1665 KB / s
16CIF	69.6 MB / s	3285 KB / s

The communication requirements of global bus change if local communication can be effectively utilised as illustrated in Table 2. The overlapped parts of the previous reconstructed picture have to be transferred between adjacent processors. An essential rule is that the reconstructed data needed in the motion estimation of one macroblock needs to be available locally or with local communication. The beginning of the encoding is similar as in the

bus architecture, but now the processors can simultaneously communicate with each other to transfer the reconstructed macroblocks of the previous picture to each other. This approach decreases global communication essentially as illustrated in Table 2. Communication requirements can be analyzed by measuring the bandwidth for global bus and ring bus data. The values are measured for the encoding speed of 30 frames per second.

5. COMPUTATIONAL REQUIREMENTS

Computational requirements in a sequential execution of one macroblock are measured using ADSP-21062 processor. The results of *Carphone.qcif* sequence are given in Table 3. Execution times vary lightly depending on the data stream, but significant differences are found only in the motion estimation step. The number of clock cycles is related to the 40 MHz system clock that are used in each PU and communication unit. The measurements show that with ADSP-21062 processor, about 10 QCIF frames per second (fps) can be encoded using new three step search (NTSS) [6]. This means that four PUs configuration would ideally reach almost 40 fps using QCIF images. The communication and synchronization overheads will, however, decrease the speedup. In PARNEU, the measured parallel efficiency is about 85 %.

Table 3 The number of clock cycles required for one macroblock encoding in ADSP-21062 processor. The used data stream is Carphone with 64 kbit/s with quantization parameter equal to 10.

Phases of inter macroblock encoding (* code is optimized using assembly language)	Clock cycles	% of total time
* Load macroblock (luminance)	400	1.0%
* Load search area (8 bit pixels→32 bit memory)	4300	10.8%
* Motion estimation (integer precision) NTSS (motion vector range [-7,7])	6100	15.3%
Bilinear interpolation of half pixel motion estimation search area	3700	9.3%
* Halfpixel motion estimation (9 locations)	3000	7.5%
Bilinear interpolation of chrominance blocks	800	2.0%
Prediction error computation	1900	4.8%
* DCT, zigzag scanning, quantization, clipping	9100	22.9%
* IDCT, inverse zigzag, inv. quantization, clipping	6800	17.1%
Reconstruction of macroblock and storing to local memory	2300	5.8%
Block level bitstream construction	1400	3.5%
Total clocks with New Three Step search	39800	100 %

The encoder was originally coded using the standard algorithms and C-language. The performance was not very good and thus the algorithms were selected more carefully and assembly coding was used. Most of the time is consumed in motion estimation, DCT and IDCT phases. Thus efficient algorithms in these phases were utilized. DCT and IDCT stages were realized with Chen's [7] fast DCT/IDCT algorithms, and several fast motion estimation algorithms were tested.

Motion estimation using new three step search algorithm was observed to be a good compromise between compression efficiency and computational burden in video conferencing applications. However, other applications can benefit from different algorithms. For example, hierarchical motion estimation

works well with noisy video. Table 4 gives the performance of 8 pixels and 15 pixels full search algorithm, three step search, new three step search [6], parallel hierarchical one-dimensional search (PHODS) [8], and hierarchical block matching motion estimation [2][9].

Several time-critical steps were assembly optimized. The hand-written assembly code was observed to be very efficient way to increase performance. The code generated by C compiler was not fast enough to achieve real time performance. The performance measurements of different motion estimation methods are presented in Table 4. The results in the left column are measured with assembly optimized block matching, while the algorithm itself was written in C-language. In the right column, the algorithm was coded completely in C language.

The hand-written assembly is efficient since ADSP-21062 is able to perform even 3 parallel computation operations and two memory read/write operations in a cycle. To utilise this computational potential needs a great effort on assembly optimization, which is time consuming but very rewarding. The greatest benefits from assembly programming were obtained in DCT, IDCT, block matching, and quantization.

It was observed that over 10% of the encoding time was consumed in the data transfer operation of loading the motion estimation search area. The load search area function reads the picture data of the motion estimation area for one macroblock and saves it to a two dimensional array. The color values of pixels are originally stored as bytes. However ADSP-21062 does not support byte wide operations and thus the color values are stored as 32-bit words to the two-dimensional array. This causes some overhead, which could be avoided if byte-wide operations were supported.

Table 4 The number of clock cycles per macroblock of different motion estimation algorithms.

Motion estimation algorithm	Assembly optimized	Fully C-code
Full search (8 pixel search distance)	49700	315200
Full search (15 pixel search distance)	135500	791400
Three Step Search	7000	51400
New Three Step Search	6100	45700
PHODS	6300	50400
Hierarchical multiresolution	-	91200

Speed estimations on newer DSP processors are very promising. Rough estimations show that real time encoding of the largest 16CIF (1408 x 1152) H.263 standard picture format can be achieved with no more than 16 Analog Device's ADSP-TS001 [10]. These estimations are based on the following: ADSP-TS001 runs at 150 MHz and it has two computational blocks. In addition ADSP-TS001 is able to perform even 16 operations on 8-bit data and read or store 32-bytes of memory in a single cycle. Compared to ADSP-21062, the performance of the new SIMD style ADSP-TS001 is about 7.5 to 60 times higher. The performance depends on the utilisation of parallel instructions but in any case the performance of the presented H.263 encoder would be dramatically increased. The communication structure of PARNEU system does not limit the performance.

6. IMPLEMENTATION IN PARNEU

The communication optimized mapping of H.263 encoder is tuned to four PUs configuration of PARNEU. MBs are distributed to PUs as shown in Figure 2. The operation starts in PARNEU after the host computer has initialized the master processor and sent the

image sequence to DRAM memory of the master card. The master fetches the first frame from the DRAM memory and sends a part of the image to each slave PU via the global bus as illustrated in Figure 3. PUs receive the MBs and start to encode their own blocks. Each PU executes the same code but for different data.

Figure 3. Program flow diagram in parallel H.263 implementation.

After encoding a MB, each PU stores the motion vectors and encoded data to its memory, from which the master PU reads the data. PUs continue in the inner loop until all MBs are encoded. After that PUs change the overlapping MBs that are needed in the motion estimation of the next frame. Block change is done via the bi-directional ring bus and thus all PUs can communicate simultaneously. Data is buffered in PUs internal memory. Neighbouring PUs are automatically synchronised because they start a new iteration only after they have received the reconstructed data blocks. Simultaneously with PU operations, the master sends an interrupt to each PU at turn and they will return the encoded data and motion information.

The bitstream must be encoded according to the sequential order of macroblocks and therefore the results are fetched row by row by the master. Each PU has an internal buffer for encoded MBs so that PUs continue encoding even though the master has not yet fetched the results of the previous row. The master combines the partially encoded data from different PUs and stores it to the DRAM memory.

Table 5 Speed measurements of PARNEU encoding using QCIF picture format. (frames per second; master + 4 PUs).

Motion estimation algorithm used in H.263 encoder	Assembly optimized	C-code
Full search (8 pixel search distance)	17.2 fps	3.9 fps
Full search (15 pixel search distance)	8.8 fps	1.7 fps
Three Step Search	34.0 fps	14.4 fps
New Three Step Search	34.6 fps	15.1 fps
PHODS	34.5 fps	15.0 fps
Hierarchical multiresolution	-	10.9 fps

Table 5 gives the measured encoding performance in four PUs PARNEU system. The left column shows assembly optimised motion estimation algorithms and the right column has C-code motion estimation algorithms. New three step search gives the best frame-rate for our test streams, but the differences to other sophisticated algorithms are quite small.

7. CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents both communication and computation requirements of H.263 video encoder. These requirements are independent of the system architecture. Utilizing local communication is important to achieve good performance.

Algorithms were tested in PARNEU to make sure that the analyses are correct. PARNEU's communication structure is good enough, but computational and memory requirements make it difficult to achieve real-time performance with large pictures. The current version of the encoder is tested mainly for QCIF pictures, but larger pictures would also achieve a real-time performance as the number of processors is increased. For QCIF pictures, over 30 fps with PARNEU configuration of the master and 4 parallel slave processors is achieved. The benefit of assembly coding is clearly indicated although C-language compilers are continuously developed.

In PARNEU, the scalability can also be preserved although the number of processors increases. The encoder is developed as linearly expandable. The computational load is distributed as evenly as possible and the memory requirements per PU decrease as the number of PUs increases. In general, the distributed memory concept works well in H.263 video encoder.

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